

Seeds

1. train-validation-test split

```
ginjinn split \  
  -I seeds \  
  -o seeds_split \  
  -d bbox-detection
```

2. generate new GinJinn2 project

```
ginjinn new seeds_split_analysis \  
  -d seeds_split \  
  -t faster_rcnn_R_101_FPN_3x.yaml
```

3. edit seeds_split_analysis/ginjinn_config.yaml
4. train model

```
ginjinn train seeds_split_analysis
```

5. evaluate model

```
ginjinn evaluate seeds_split_analysis
```

6. (optional) predict on test dataset (or new images)

```
ginjinn predict seeds_split_analysis \  
  -i seeds_split/test/images  
  -o seeds_split_test_prediction \  
  -c -v
```

Stickytraps

1. train-validation-test split

```
ginjinn split \  
  -I stickytraps \  
  -o stickytraps_split \  
  -d bbox-detection
```

2. sliding-window cropping

```
ginjinn utils sw_split \  
  -I stickytraps_split \  
  -o stickytraps_split_sw \  
  -s 1024 -p 256 -c
```

3. generate new GinJinn2 project

```
ginjinn new stickytraps_split_sw_analysis \  
  -d stickytraps_split_sw \  
  -t faster_rcnn_R_101_FPN_3x.yaml
```

4. edit stickytraps_split_sw_analysis/ginjinn_config.yaml

5. train model

```
ginjinn train stickytraps_split_sw_analysis
```

6. evaluate model ginjinn evaluate stickytraps_split_sw_analysis

7. (optional) predict on test images (or new images)

7.1 sliding-window crop images

```
ginjinn utils sw_split \  
-i stickytraps_split_sw/test/images/ \  
-o sticktraps_newdata_sw \  
-s 1024 -p 256
```

7.2 detect bounding boxes

```
ginjinn predict stickytraps_split_sw_analysis \  
-i sticktraps_newdata_sw \  
-o sticktraps_newdata_sw_prediction \  
-c -v
```

7.3 (optional) merge sliding-window predictions to reconstruct predictions on original images

```
ginjinn utils sw_merge \  
-a sticktraps_newdata_sw_prediction/annotations.json \  
-i sticktraps_newdata_sw \  
-o sticktraps_newdata_sw_prediction_merged \  
-t bbox-detection
```

7.4 (optional) visualization of the merged predictions

```
ginjinn vis \  
-I sticktraps_newdata_sw_prediction_merged \  
-v bbox
```

Stomata

1. train-validation-test split

```
ginjinn split \  
-I stomata \  
-o stomata_split \  
-d instance-segmentation
```

2. generate new GinJinn2 project

```
ginjinn new stomata_split_analysis \  
-d stomata_split \  
-t mask_rcnn_R_101_FPN_3x.yaml
```

3. edit stomata_split_analysis/ginjinn_config.yaml
4. train model

```
ginjinn train stomata_split_analysis
```

5. evaluate model

```
ginjinn evaluate stomata_split_analysis
```

6. (optional) predict on test images (or new images)

```
ginjinn predict stomata_split_analysis \  
-i stomata_split/test/images \  
-o stomata_prediction \  
-c -v
```

Leucanthemum

1. flatten CVAT output

```
ginjinn utils flatten \  
-i leucanthemum/images/ \  
-a leucanthemum/annotations/instances_default.json \  
-o leucanthemum_flat
```

2. remove empty categories

```
ginjinn info -I leucanthemum_flat  
ginjinn utils filter_cat \  
-a leucanthemum_flat/annotations.json \  
-i leucanthemum_flat/images/ \  
-o leucanthemum_flat_filtered \  
-d -f main_vein  
ginjinn info -I leucanthemum_flat_filtered
```

3. train-validation-test split

```
ginjinn split \  
-I leucanthemum_flat_filtered \  
-o leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split \  
-d instance-segmentation
```

4. bounding-box model

- 4.1 sliding-window cropping

```
ginjinn utils sw_split \  
-I leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split \  
-o leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_sw \  
-s 2056 -p 512 -c
```

- 4.2 generate new GinJinn2 project

```
ginjinn new leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_sw_analysis \  
-t faster_rcnn_R_101_FPN_3x.yaml \  
-d leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_sw
```

4.3 edit leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_sw_analysis/ginjinn_config.yaml

4.4 train model

```
ginjinn train leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_sw_analysis
```

4.5 evaluate model

```
ginjinn evaluate leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_sw_analysis
```

4.6 (optional) predict on test dataset

```
ginjinn predict leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_sw_analysis \  
-i leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_sw/test/images \  
-o leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_sw_test_prediction \  
-c -v
```

4.7 (optional) merge sliding-window predictions to reconstruct predictions on original images

```
ginjinn utils sw_merge \  
-a leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_sw_test_prediction/annotations.json \  
-i leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_sw/test/images \  
-o leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_sw_test_prediction_merged \  
-t bbox-detection
```

4.8 (optional) visualization of the merged predictions

```
ginjinn vis \  
-I leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_sw_test_prediction_merged \  
-v bbox
```

5. segmentation model

5.1 bounding box cropping

```
ginjinn utils crop \  
-I leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split \  
-o leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_cropped \  
-t segmentation \  
-p 25
```

5.2 generate new GinJinn2 project

```
ginjinn new leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_cropped_analysis \  
-t mask_rcnn_R_101_FPN_3x.yaml \  
-d leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_cropped
```

5.3 edit leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_cropped_analysis/ginjinn_config.yaml

5.4 train model

```
ginjinn train leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_cropped_analysis
```

5.5 evaluate model

```
ginjinn evaluate leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_cropped_analysis
```

5.6 (optional) predict on test dataset

```
ginjinn predict leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_cropped_analysis \  
-i leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_cropped/test/images \  
-o leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_cropped_test_prediction \  
-c -v
```

6. apply both models sequentially to new images (here test images for demonstration purposes)

6.1 sliding-window cropping

```
ginjinn utils sw_split \  
-i leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split/test/images/ \  
-o leucanthemum_newdata_sw \  
-s 2056 -p 512
```

6.2 bounding-box detection

```
ginjinn predict leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_sw_analysis \  
-i leucanthemum_newdata_sw \  
-o leucanthemum_newdata_sw_prediction \  
-c -v
```

6.3 merge sliding-windows

```
ginjinn utils sw_merge \  
-a leucanthemum_newdata_sw_prediction/annotations.json \  
-i leucanthemum_newdata_sw \  
-o leucanthemum_newdata_sw_prediction_merged \  
-t bbox-detection
```

6.4 crop bounding boxes

```
ginjinn utils crop \  
-I leucanthemum_newdata_sw_prediction_merged \  
-o leucanthemum_newdata_sw_prediction_merged_cropped \  
-t bbox \  
-p 25
```

6.5 segmentation with refinement

```
ginjinn predict leucanthemum_flat_filtered_split_cropped_analysis \  
-i leucanthemum_newdata_sw_prediction_merged_cropped/images \  
-o leucanthemum_newdata_segmentation_prediction \  
-c -v \  
-r
```